

Falungong 法輪功 (Falun Gong) / Falun Dafa 法輪大法

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Falungong 法輪功 ("Dharma Wheel Practice"), also romanized as Falun Gong and alternatively named Falun Dafa 法輪大法 ("Great Teachings of the Dharma Wheel"), was founded in 1992 by Li Hongzhi 李鴻志 (b. 1950 or 1951) in China's northeastern Jilin Province 吉林省. What sets it apart from other Qigong groups of that time is its unique blend of traditions. In addition to creatively interpreting physical and spiritual self-cultivation practices from Daoist and Buddhist antecedents, Li's teachings also draw on messianic and apocalyptic tropes from China's rich sectarian traditions, Western New Age, and the belief in the interference of aliens. The practice centers on the idea of a revolving "dharma wheel" (falun 法輪) that Li plants inside the practitioner's abdomen, which, being stimulated through Falungong practice, can absorb and emit energy. Even though different in terms of conceptualization, the symbol of the "dharma wheel" (Skt. dharmacakra) is borrowed from Buddhism, where it is used to represent the Buddhist teachings. At the same time, Falungong is much more than a set of physical and spiritual regimens of self-actualization. Instead, the doctrines put forth in Li's core scriptures, especially Zhuan Falun 轉法輪 (The Dharma Wheel Revolves), center on the tripartite moral concept of zhen 真 (truth or truthfulness), shan 善 (compassion, goodness), and ren 忍 (forbearance). They are the very nature of the cosmos and the organizing principle of all things. Because humans and all living beings have been morally corrupted when they entered the mundane world, their greed and attachment bound them to the endless cycle of transmigration (the Buddhist concept of saṃsāra), which is why this primordial perfect state has been forgotten. Falungong practitioners aspire to actualize their inherent moral potential. Accordingly, zhen, shan, and ren represent not only ethical qualities for individuals and society at large but also cosmological properties. Furthermore, Li's writings are emersed in apocalyptic themes, messianic tropes, and morally conservative ideals that strongly oppose modern Western liberal values. Accordingly, several researchers have noted that some of Li's teachings are not merely conservative but inherently racist, misogynist, sexist, and homophobic. The history of Falungong is deeply tied to the post-Mao Qigong craze that swept the country until the Chinese Communist Party's (CCP) crackdown on the movement ended this wave in the late 1990s. Qigong 氣功 ("Qi practice") is based on much older traditions of bodily and spiritual practices related to physical care, but, as a modernized system, it was specifically created in 1949 by CCP researchers to provide a reasonable solution to the pressing issues of public health. At that time, the party sought to bereave these practices of all religious and spiritual elements because they were deemed "feudal superstitions" and "backward elements." In the post-Mao period, however, Qigong experienced a nuanced spiritual turn. During the 1980s and 1990s, the Qigong movement was instrumental in fostering what is generally referred to as the period of the "religious fever" (zongjiaore 宗教熱), during which diverse religious and spiritual movements tried to fill the ideological void created by the disappearance of high Maoism. Within a few years, Falungong became one of China's most successful Qigong movements, and by the late 1990s, it had already spread to other countries. At that time, the CCP estimated between 2.1 and 2.3 million followers in China alone. Retrospectively, Falungong sources claim up to 80 million followers at that time. However, these numbers are not grounded in solid statistics but seem motivated by the desire to outnumber the CCP, which had approximately 58 to 63 million members during the late 1990s and early 2000s. In the wake of the 1999 crackdown and the ongoing anticampaign in China, many practitioners were forced underground, forsake

their faith publicly, or leave the country. Since then, Falungong has emerged as a global movement with local chapters in various countries. New York City represents the crucial hub in the movement's transnational network, probably because Li and his family moved there in 1996. Accordingly, it comes as no surprise that the Falungong headquarters, "Dragon Springs" (Longquan 龍泉), is located in Orange County, New York. Furthermore, most internet outlets and affiliated enterprises—such as the print and online newspaper The Epoch Times (established in August 2000), the broadcasting company "New Tang Dynasty TV" (since February 2002), and the publishing house Minghui—are all but located in New York. Today, Falungong and its affiliated enterprises are a transnational conglomerate that includes media enterprises, public relations firms, and commercial operations. These enterprises and Falungong's extensive volunteer mobilization culture support the movement's more significant cause of unmasking the Communist regime in Beijing and its atrocities. Even though many of these are well-documented, critical voices lament that the movement's strongly biased perspective and hardline anticommunist agenda represent a propagandistic approach by itself. In the late 1990s and early 2000s, Falungong received international media coverage after over 10,000 participants assembled in front of the CCP headquarters at Zhongnanhai 中南海, next to the Forbidden City in Beijing, on April 25, 1999, to peacefully demonstrate for the release of fellow practitioners who had been incarcerated a few days earlier. Even though this unprecedented event caught the CCP off guard, party and government institutions and media outlets instigated the largest anti-campaign in PRC history in only three months. Because the number of those affected by this ongoing campaign released by the government and by Falungong activists differ significantly, there is only little reliable information. According to activists, five thousand practitioners were killed in these campaigns until June 2023, and there are hundreds of thousands, if not millions, who were detained to "labor reeducation" or were subject to torture, abuse, and organ harvesting. Yet, the scope of organ harvesting and the existence of specific "concentration camps" is cast into doubt by some scholars and human rights activists. From the early stage of Falungong's resistance against the CCP, activists used the Internet to pursue global activism. Only a few months after the June 1999 crackdown, practitioners in the United States founded the website "Clear Wisdom" (minghuiwang 明慧網), which is specially designed to track the evolving campaign and its response by Falungong activists worldwide. The site is currently (as of April 2024) available in 22 different languages, which further attests to the movement's global appeal. In August 2000, practitioners founded The Epoch Times (Dajiyuan 大紀元), which quickly evolved into the most widely distributed Chinese newspaper in North America and, since 2016, has shifted towards ultraconservative and far-right topics in their Western-language editions in the United States and Europe. Today, Falungong-affiliated media enterprises comprise various websites, newspapers, news portals (Radio Free Asia), and streaming services (such as Epoch TV) that rally the movement's greater cause to win the support of ultraconservative Christians and other right-wing forces to form an anti-China coalition.

Date Range: 1992 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Changchun City 長春市, Jilin Province 吉林省

Region tags: Asia, China, Jilin

In Changchun, the provincial capital of Jilin in northeastern China, Li Hongzhi first revealed his teachings and practices that later evolved into Falungong to the public.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Ownby, David. Falun Gong and the Future of China. New York, Oxford: Oxford University Press,

2008.

- Source 2: Penny, Benjamin. *The Religion of Falun Gong*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2012.
- Source 3: Palmer, David A. *Qigong Fever: Body, Science, and Utopia in China*. New York: Columbia University Press, 2007.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://freedomhouse.org/report/2017/battle-china-spirit-falun-gong-religious-freedom>
- Source 1 Description: 2017 Freedom House Report: "Falun Gong: Religious Freedom in China"

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://en.falundafa.org/>
- Source 1 Description: Collection of Falungong books and publications, English translations, also available in 53 languages. Download available for free.
- Source 2 URL: <https://en.minghui.org/>
- Source 2 Description: "Clear Wisdom" (Minghuiwang 明慧網), Falungong activist site, tracks the evolving anticampaign and its response by Falungong activists worldwide, 22 languages.
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.zhuichaguoji.org/>
- Source 3 Description: 追查迫害法輪功國際組織 / World Organization to Investigate the Persecution of Falun Gong (Falungong activist site)

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– No

Notes: Even though Li Hongzhi's teachings draw on a wide range of religious and other influences from Buddhism and Daoism, as well as the Western New Age, they exhibit a sense of exclusivity and prohibit practitioners from studying other physical practices, including Taijiquan 太極拳. Likewise, going to regular Chinese temples, using talismans, and donating money to other religious organizations is forbidden.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 7000000

Notes: No statistics are available, but various sources, including Falungong-affiliated ones, estimate between 7 and 20 million regular practitioners worldwide.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (intolerant of other affiliations)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Very little is known about Li Hongzhi and his inner circle of leaders.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– Yes

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

↳ Powers are inherited:

– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– No

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: When Li Hongzhi disappeared from the public in July 1999 for almost one year, following the CCP crackdown on Falungong in June, some practitioners openly questioned his leadership.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:
– Yes

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:
– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:
– Yes

↳ Are they oral:
– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:
– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:
– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:
– No

↳ Inspired by high god:
– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

Notes: Some early scriptures, such as China Falun Gong, have been slightly amended after their first publication.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Notes: There is a canon, which consists of Li's scriptures and lectures, but they are not formally codified.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Notes: Images and statues of deities, Buddhas, and bodhisattvas are not used; yet, the Buddhist "dharma wheel" symbol (dharmacakra) is ubiquitous in Falungong publications and websites.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: According to Li's magnum opus Zhuan Falun 轉法輪, every human being possesses an imperishable "original spirit"(yuanshen 元神). He argues that this is the part of all sentient beings who survive death and are reborn. It gives human beings sentience, intelligence, and purpose. Without this yuanshen, a human being is just a "lump of flesh" without individual character. Sometimes, he further distinguishes a "chief original spirit" (zhuyuanshen 主元神) and a "deputy original spirit" (fuyuanshen 副元神). The term "yuanshen" originated in Daoism, but has been used there slightly different in the sense of someone's "true self" that the practitioners needs to cultivate. By contrast, Benjamin Penny has noted that this concept has been gradually adapted by Li to fit Western understandings of the "soul."

Reference: Penny, Benjamin. The Religion of Falun Gong. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2012. p.118-121

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Li Hongzhi teaches that humans possess a soul-like entity, the "original spirit" (yuanshen 元神). Unlike the physical body, this element of one's self does not perish at death but is reborn into the next existence.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Falungong practitioners believe that successful self-cultivation leads to "returning to the origin" (huanben 還本), a concept derived from Daoism that posits that successful practitioners are able to restore their primordial, original self that is seen superior to the mundane transitory existence. Li's teachings claim that, in primordial times, humans have been divinities of some sort (either Buddhas, "Daos" (dao 道), or gods (shen 神)). Because of inevitable social interaction and misconduct, they degraded from the upper realms of the cosmos that are variously defined as paradises. According to Li, Falungong practices enables followers to re-ascend to their original state and regain their god-like statuses. This ultimate aim of Falungong practitioners is called "consummation" (yuanman 圓滿).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:
– Yes

Notes: Those who have achieved the "Consummation" (yuanman 圓滿) through intense self-cultivation will "return to the origin" (a Daoist trope) and leave this mundane dimension of the cosmos to regain their original forms as Buddhas or deities.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:
– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:
– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:
– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:
– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: Li's understanding of reincarnation draws on established Buddhist concepts that are widely accepted in Chinese religious contexts. Yet, he also deliberately departs from the default understanding in many ways. For instance, he claims that humans may also be reborn as plants and innate substances. By contrast, even though there has been a longstanding debate in Buddhism about the sentience of plants, these two entities are not generally accepted as part of the "six paths of reincarnation" (Ch. liudao 六道), i.e., 1) gods, 2) humans, 3) demigods (asuras), 4) animals, 5) hungry ghosts, 6) beings in the hells.

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Field doesn't know

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: According to Li's teachings, in primordial times, humans were divine beings, such as "Buddhas" (fo 佛), "Daos" (dao 道), and "deities/spirits" (shen 神). These reside in the upper realms of the cosmos. By successfully cultivating themselves through Falungong practice, practitioners may achieve the ultimate aim of "consummation" (yuanman 圓滿), by which they regain their primordial godly status.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Different kinds of non-human supernatural beings are present in Li Hongzhi's writings. For instance, he believes animals cannot cultivate themselves properly because they don't possess human bodies. Therefore, the only way for them to progress in their cultivation is by possessing the bodies of humans and absorbing their energies. Some of these animals transform into demons and evil beings that haunt other humans and cause trouble. Others keep on possessing humans, but ordinary humans are not able to identify them. Accordingly, but without dropping names, Li claims that many renowned Buddhist masters in Taiwan are demons, supposed Indian masters are possessed by giant pythons, and even many qigong masters in China are possessed by foxes and weasels. Li's reference to foxes is especially noteworthy, as, in premodern China, foxes were generally believed to deceit and possess human beings, especially in the form of beautiful women seducing men. Furthermore, Li has repeatedly referred to extraterrestrial beings ("aliens") that have infiltrated human societies. His descriptions have slightly changed since he first mentioned them in the mid-1990s. While initially described as beings piloting flying saucers that employ superior technology to travel between dimensions, his later views reflect a more profound engagement with Western UFO mythology. Thus, he claims that scientific technology ultimately derives from extraterrestrial sources, and it has been employed by aliens who live undetected in our societies to control humans. According to his understanding, these aliens seek to interbreed with humans to create a superior race of intergalactic hybrids. He also believes that various governments, especially that of the United States, are well aware of alien visits and sometimes even collude with them. It is difficult to ascertain how Li's understanding of alien interference came into being, but he was likely influenced by both Chinese translations of popular Western UFO-related publications (such as the ones by the well-known Swiss author Erich von Däniken (b. 1935)) and well-known TV shows, such as *The X-Files* (1993-2002).

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - No
- ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other organization for pantheon:
 - Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

- ↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Adultery:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Incest:
 - Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: homosexuality

Notes: Li Hongzhi has repeatedly argued that homosexuality represents an abnormality that goes against the standards that the gods gave to humankind. He even claimed that the first target that gods will terminate at the end of times will be homosexuals.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: As in many other Chinese religious contexts, deities are perceived as punishing those who act against the moral cosmos.

- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - No
 - ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other [specify]
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
 - Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

- Field doesn't know

Notes: In theory, the spiritual achievements of Falungong practitioners depend on their practice's quality and commitment to it.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

- Yes

- ↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?
 - Yes

- ↳ Alive, identified:
 - Yes

Notes: Li Hongzhi is considered by many to be the savior. Falungong practitioners believe that Li is more than an ordinary spiritual teacher but who possesses superhuman powers like flying and invisibility. According to internal sources published in the mid-1990s, Li was born on May 13, 1951, a date that coincides with the historical Buddha's birthday that Chinese Buddhists celebrate according to the traditional lunisolar calendar on the 8th day of the 4th month. Li's followers accept this as proof of his messianic mission. By contrast, Chinese authorities claim that the birthday has been changed by Falungong practitioners and that Li was born on Juli 27, 1952.

- ↳ Coming in this lifetime:
 - No

- ↳ Coming on specified date:
 - No

- ↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:
 - No

- ↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:
 - No

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– No

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: Saving the universe

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

Notes: Yet, according to Li Hongzhi's writings, we already live in the "final period of the dharma," as is evident by humankind's moral corruption and spiritual degeneration. Furthermore, he believes that modern science is employed by aliens to control humankind. Collective karmic debt, accumulated over generations, have led to this devastating situation.

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– No

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: As stated above, Li stated that homosexuals will be the first targets of the gods' wrath.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– No

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Notes: Shan 善 (compassion, goodness) is one of three crucial values that are promoted by Falungong.

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– No

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– I don't know

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– No

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– No

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

Notes: Ren 忍 (forbearance) is third in Falungong's list of three crucial values (these are zhen, shan, and ren). While initially related to how practitioners deal with individual hardships, the collective experience of suppression provided a vast arena to demonstrate one's forbearance in the face of government oppression and violence. Accordingly, this "tribulation" is considered valuable in practitioners' self-cultivation.

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– No

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

↳ Humility / modesty:

– No

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– No

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– No

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

Notes: Especially Chinese Falungong practitioners worldwide share the desire to replace the Communist government in China and to show the world how "China before Communism" was (which is a slogan of the Falungong-related performing arts troupe Shen Yun).

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– I don't know

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– No

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– No

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– No

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual

abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: Yet, sacrificing oneself for Falungong's more significant cause is especially valued by coreligionists. Enduring hardships and pain without forsaking one's faith is at the heart of one of the movement's three crucial values, ren 忍 (forbearance).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: It is not required, but donating money and other valuable resources to the greater cause is highly appreciated by coreligionists.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: On the surface, Falungong practitioners appear as peaceful protesters in the streets of many cities worldwide. However, some critics argue that internal conversation in the inner circle differs fundamentally from the movement's outward image. Scholars such as the late scholar of new religious movements, James R. Lewis, claims that Li and his peers encourage practitioners to seek brutalization. According to his understanding, the more practitioners are brutalized by the Chinese state, the higher they rank in the eyes of Falungong leaders.

Reference: Lewis, James R.. *Falun Gong: Spiritual Warfare and Martyrdom*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2018.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: There is no formal ceremony (like in Buddhism), but the tripartite moral concepts of zhen 真 (truth/truthfulness), shan 善 (compassion), and ren 忍 (forbearance) are promoted as the central pillar of Falungong's moral teachings.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Notes: There are many cases in which Falungong critics have been slandered and targeted by psychological pressure by Falungong activists. Committed practitioners seem to exhibit a strong impetus to dividing in-group from out-group, which is especially visible regarding public discourses about the movement.

Reference: Farley, Helen. "Falun Gong's Attack on Academic Freedom". In *Enlightened Martyrdom: The Hidden Side of Falun Gong*. Sheffield, UK: Equinox Publishing, 2019.

Reference: Kavan, Heather. "Friendly Fire: How Falun Gong Mistook Me for an Enemy". In *Enlightened Martyrdom: The Hidden Side of Falun Gong*. Sheffield, UK: Equinox Publishing, 2019.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Little is known about how Falungong is actually organized internally. While it appears to be only loosely organized, the number of highly streamlined and profitable enterprises (websites, news portals, newspapers, streaming services, performing arts troupes, etc.), the corporate identity, and the global "branding" of Falungong suggest that the inner circle of leaders is highly organized.

Reference: Tong, James. "An Organizational Analysis of the Falun Gong: Structure, Communications, Financing". *The China Quarterly*, no. 171 (2002): 636–60.

<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1017/S0009443902000402>.

Reference: Junker, Andrew. *Becoming Activists in Global China: Social Movements in the Chinese Diaspora*. New York: Cambridge University Press, 2019.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

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